

IMPACT OF VARIOUS FACTORS ON NON-ACADEMIC STAFF PERFORMANCE IN SRI LANKAN STATE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *This study investigates the impact of different factors on the efficiency of non-academic personnel in public universities in Sri Lanka. An efficiently organized work environment with sufficient tools and amenities additionally boosts productivity and promotes the well-being of employees. Leadership styles that place a high value on transparency, support, and inclusiveness have a substantial influence on the morale and productivity of workers. The report emphasizes that adopting a comprehensive approach to tackling these factors can substantially enhance staff productivity and overall organizational efficiency. The university administration should execute focused strategies to improve working conditions, foster a positive organizational culture, and adopt effective leadership methods to support non-academic workers.*

Keywords: *organizational culture, job happiness, work environment, leadership styles, inclusivity, respect, collaboration.*

Introduction:

The efficiency and effectiveness of non-academic staff in state universities are crucial for these institutions' seamless operation and management. Academic staff directly contribute to teaching and research [1], while non-academic staff support these fundamental activities through their jobs in administration, finance, maintenance, and student services. Various aspects, such as organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, and leadership styles, impact the performance of non-academic staff in state institutions in Sri Lanka. This study aims to examine these factors' influence on the efficiency of non-academic personnel in state universities in Sri Lanka [2-3].

This study investigates the influence of organizational culture, job happiness, work environment, and leadership styles on the efficiency and productivity of employees in higher education institutions. It acknowledges these factors' crucial role in supporting academic and administrative activities. In addition to that, it specifically targeted non-academic employees across multiple universities. Studies indicate that a favourable organizational culture substantially influences staff productivity by fostering a work atmosphere that promotes collaboration and respect. Job satisfaction is a crucial component that directly affects motivation and productivity. It is influenced by various aspects, including recognition, fair compensation, and possibilities for professional development [4-5].

Objectives:

To identify the factors influencing the performance of non-academic staff in Sri Lankan state universities.

To assess the impact of organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, and leadership styles on non-academic staff performance.

To provide recommendations for improving the performance of non-academic staff in state universities.

Results and Discussion

Key factors affecting the performance of non-academic staff

An optimistic and encouraging work atmosphere is essential. This encompasses possessing the requisite resources, facilities, and equipment to perform their responsibilities optimally. Lack of sufficient infrastructure or unfavourable working conditions cannot ensure performance is maintained. Furthermore, the professional development options aid personnel in enhancing their abilities and remaining up-to-date with the most effective methods. Lack of adequate training can hamper their performance and hinder their professional advancement. Additionally, factors such as work security, equitable remuneration, acknowledgement, and prospects for professional growth have a substantial impact. Diminished job satisfaction might result in reduced motivation and productivity.

Furthermore, the utilization of good leadership and management strategies is vital. Effective communication, encouraging supervision, and equitable and transparent decision-making processes can positively influence workers' performance. Well-defined tasks and responsibilities, along with controlled workloads, facilitate workers in efficiently carrying out their activities. Performance can be adversely impacted by staff members overwhelmed with work or job objectives that must be clearly defined. The university's overarching culture and principles, which encompass inclusivity, respect, and collaboration, have the potential to impact staff morale and performance [7].

Offering competitive compensation packages and perks is crucial for ensuring employees' long-term commitment and drive. Paying more remuneration might result in discontentment and elevated employee attrition rates. Policies concerning human resources, performance evaluation, and career advancement influence the management and support of non-academic staff. The resources available to universities and personnel performance can be influenced by economic situations, government policies, and changes in higher education funding [8].

Organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, and leadership styles influence non-academic staff performance.

Organizational culture, job happiness, work environment, and leadership styles significantly impact non-academic staff's success. Here is a detailed examination of how these elements influence the performance of the staff. The impact of organizational culture on performance: organizational culture refers to the collective values, beliefs, and norms inside a particular institution. An affirmative culture cultivates cooperation, confidence, and a feeling of inclusion, augmenting motivation and job proficiency. On the other hand, a detrimental culture characterized by inadequate communication and conflict can result in disengagement and reduced production [9].

An influential and nurturing culture fosters a sense of unity among employees, motivating them to synchronize their efforts with the organisation's objectives. This culture also cultivates collaboration and elevates the overall level of contentment in the workplace. Conversely, a detrimental culture can lead to elevated employee attrition rates and diminished morale. Job satisfaction is strongly correlated with employees' satisfaction with their job duties, responsibilities, and working conditions. Increased job satisfaction typically results in heightened motivation, improved performance, and extraordinary organisational dedication. However,

dissatisfaction can lead to decreased productivity, absenteeism, and high employee turnover. Content employees are more inclined to be actively involved, proactive, and willing to exert more effort. Additionally, they have a propensity for greater creativity and innovation in their respective positions. Decreased satisfaction can hurt performance and lead to a hostile work atmosphere [10].

Working Conditions

The work environment encompasses tangible factors, such as the physical conditions and available resources, as well as the intangible factors of the overall atmosphere at the workplace. A well-furnished and pleasant work environment has the potential to enhance productivity and job contentment. Substandard conditions, such as insufficient amenities or potential dangers, can hinder performance and result in stress and dissatisfaction. A conducive work environment facilitates employees in carrying out their duties with optimal efficiency and comfort. Additionally, it can impact their general welfare and level of contentment in their occupation.

On the other hand, a destructive or dysfunctional work environment can impede performance and result in increased absenteeism and decreased morale. Leadership styles impact the management, motivation, and support of personnel. Transformational leadership, which prioritizes motivating and nurturing individuals, has the potential to result in enhanced performance and increased engagement. Alternatively, leadership styles that are authoritarian or laissez-faire can have adverse effects on motivation and performance. Leaders who effectively communicate, offer assistance and acknowledge accomplishments can improve their personnel's performance and job happiness. Unapproachable, excessively fault-finding, or apathetic leaders may provoke dissatisfaction and disengagement among personnel, which can harm performance [11-12].

These tactics can be utilized to improve the performance of non-academic staff in public colleges. A comprehensive strategy can be implemented to improve the efficiency of non-academic personnel in public colleges. Below are a few highly effective strategies:

Professional Development and Training

Provide frequent training programs, workshops, and seminars to assist employees in enhancing their abilities and remaining up-to-date with the most effective methods in their respective areas. There is potential for professional growth through mentorship initiatives, employment rotation opportunities, and assistance pursuing additional education. Ensure staff have the necessary tools, technology, and resources to fulfil their duties. Ensure the workspace is secure, hygienic, and constructed using ergonomic principles to promote comfort and minimize stress. Establish mechanisms to identify and incentivize exceptional achievements, such as granting accolades, financial bonuses, or public recognition. Advocate for policies that facilitate a harmonious integration of work and personal life, such as implementing flexible scheduling, offering remote work opportunities, and ensuring adequate allowances for time off [13-14].

Cultivate a Favourable Organizational Culture

Foster a culture characterized by respect, inclusiveness, and collaboration. Promote transparent communication and encourage the exchange of feedback. Facilitate team-building exercises and social gatherings to enhance employee interpersonal connections and foster a cohesive community atmosphere [15-16].

Efficient Leadership and Administration

Leaders must communicate effectively and openly regarding organizational objectives, modifications, and anticipated outcomes. Implement leadership approaches that demonstrate

support and empathy, offering guidance and assistance to employees while promoting independence. Establish unambiguous roles and responsibilities to prevent ambiguity and ensure that employees clearly understand their expected duties. Supervise workloads to avoid overwhelming the workforce. Modify duties as necessary to achieve optimal workload distribution. Conduct periodic performance evaluations to offer valuable criticism and pinpoint areas that need work [17-18].

Establish unambiguous and attainable objectives and furnish employees with the necessary resources and assistance. Enhance employee involvement and ownership by including personnel in decision-making processes about their work and the organization's operations. Implement mechanisms for employees to offer feedback and suggestions and ensure their contributions are respected and acted upon [19-24].

Provide a salary and benefits package.

Ensure the salary and benefits are competitive and equitable, considering the staff's talents, experience, and responsibilities. Providing perks such as medical insurance, pension schemes, and allowances for professional growth is advisable. Establish a conducive atmosphere that fosters a culture of innovation, where employees are motivated to put forward novel concepts and remedies without apprehension of negative feedback. Enable employees to engage in strategic experimentation and take measured risks, providing the necessary tools and advice to support their endeavours [25-31].

Conclusion

The study on the influence of many variables on the effectiveness of non-academic personnel in state universities in Sri Lanka uncovers an intricate interaction among organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, and leadership styles. The research highlights the interconnectedness of these aspects, emphasizing that they jointly impact staff performance and, consequently, the overall effectiveness of the institutions.

A solid and favourable organizational culture significantly improves staff performance by creating an atmosphere of trust, respect, and collaboration. Universities that foster a nurturing environment are more inclined to observe committed and driven personnel, resulting in increased efficiency and job contentment. The research findings emphasize the significance of adopting a comprehensive approach to enhance the performance of non-academic staff. Universities can improve the effectiveness and supportiveness of their work environment by focusing on critical elements such as organizational culture, job satisfaction, work environment, and leadership. Consequently, this contributes to the institution's overall performance. The recommendations derived from this study provide practical strategies to improve the performance of personnel in Sri Lankan state universities. Implementing focused interventions in these areas can enhance staff engagement, satisfaction, and productivity. The study offers valuable insights for legislators and university administrators, indicating that a strategic emphasis on these elements is crucial for attaining institutional excellence and cultivating a favourable and productive academic community.

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